

Smart Grid-Connected Solar System for Home Loads and BLDC Motor Applications Using MATLAB

Dr.Ch.Rambabu, B.Sravya, B.Sravanthi, G.Sandeep, J.Jeevan

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Vasireddy Venkatadri Institute of Technology, Pedakakani, Namburu, Guntur, India

To Cite this Article

Dr.Ch.Rambabu, B.Sravya, B.Sravanthi, G.Sandeep & J.Jeevan (2025). Smart Grid-Connected Solar System for Home Loads and BLDC Motor Applications Using MATLAB. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(04), 436-443. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189874>

Article Info

Received: 11 March 2025; Accepted: 05 April 2025; Published: 09 April 2025.

Copyright © The Authors ; This is an open access article distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

KEYWORDS

Solar Power Generation, Grid-Connected System, Smart Energy Management, Home Appliances, BLDC Motor, MATLAB/Simulink, Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), Photovoltaic (PV) System, Voltage Source Inverter (VSI), Power quality, Power factor, Total harmonic distortion.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and simulation of a smart grid-connected solar energy system for powering residential loads and operating a Brushless DC (BLDC) motor using MATLAB/Simulink. The proposed system utilizes photovoltaic (PV) panels as the primary energy source, efficiently managed through a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm to ensure optimal energy extraction under varying irradiance conditions. A DC-DC converter boosts the PV voltage, while a voltage source inverter (VSI) interfaces the system with the utility grid for seamless power exchange. The grid-connected configuration enables the system to supply power to household appliances while also supporting a BLDC motor used for domestic applications such as water pumping or ventilation. The motor is controlled through an efficient electronic commutation strategy, ensuring smooth and energy-saving operation. The system intelligently manages power flow, supplying loads directly from the solar source when available and switching to grid support during low solar generation periods. Simulation results in MATLAB validate the effectiveness of the design in terms of voltage stability, current response, efficient power sharing, and reliable motor performance. The proposed smart solar-grid hybrid system offers a sustainable and energy-efficient solution for modern households, reducing grid dependency and contributing to clean energy usage

1. INTRODUCTION

The rising global demand for energy, along with the pressing need to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, has led to a significant shift towards renewable energy

technologies. Among various renewable options, solar photovoltaic (PV) systems have gained immense popularity due to their clean nature, modularity, and suitability for both urban and rural deployments [1], [2].

Solar PV offers a decentralized and scalable solution, particularly in residential environments, where energy independence and sustainability are increasingly prioritized [3], [4]. Grid-connected PV systems offer a dual advantage: they not only allow users to generate their own electricity but also to feed surplus power back into the grid through net metering arrangements [5]. This integration improves power system reliability, reduces peak load stress, and promotes cleaner power generation [6], [7]. Technological advancements in power electronics and control systems, especially through simulation platforms like MATLAB/Simulink, have significantly enhanced the development and evaluation of such grid-integrated renewable systems [8], [9]. A key requirement in PV systems is to ensure maximum utilization of available solar energy. Due to the inherently nonlinear characteristics of PV arrays and their sensitivity to environmental parameters like irradiance and temperature, Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms are implemented to extract the optimal power at any given time [10], [11]. Among various MPPT methods, Perturb and Observe (P&O) and Incremental Conductance are the most commonly applied in practical systems due to their simplicity and reliability [12], [13]. These algorithms, when implemented with DC-DC converters like boost converters, ensure a continuous supply of maximum power from PV panels under dynamically changing conditions [14], [15]. Another essential component in residential energy systems is the integration of efficient motor technologies. Brushless DC (BLDC) motors have emerged as a superior alternative to conventional motors, especially in low- and medium-power applications [16]. Their high torque-to-weight ratio, low maintenance, silent operation, and better thermal performance make them ideal for home appliances such as fans, pumps, washing machines, and even electric vehicles [17], [18]. BLDC motors operate on DC supply, which perfectly aligns with the output nature of solar PV systems, minimizing conversion losses and enhancing system compatibility [19]. In a smart solar-powered home environment, energy flow management is crucial. The Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) plays a pivotal role in converting the DC output of the PV system to AC, which is suitable for both grid synchronization and powering AC-based home loads [20], [21]. The inverter is also responsible for maintaining output voltage and

frequency stability while ensuring low Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), which is essential for maintaining power quality [22], [23]. Numerous research efforts have investigated the integration of PV systems with BLDC motors for various applications. For instance, a BLDC motor-driven solar water pumping system was proposed in [24], demonstrating improved efficiency under changing environmental conditions. Similarly, [25] presented a comprehensive MATLAB-based model for grid-tied solar systems with domestic load management using MPPT-based control strategies. In such systems, the performance of MPPT algorithms directly influences the efficiency of motor operations and household energy distribution [26]. To enable real-time monitoring and control, digital control units such as microcontrollers or DSPs are used, which execute MPPT and inverter control algorithms [27]. MATLAB/Simulink is commonly used for simulation and testing of these systems before hardware implementation, offering a safe and versatile platform for performance evaluation, fault testing, and control validation [28], [29]. The use of BLDC motors in solar-powered home systems has been further supported by improved motor drive circuits and electronic commutation techniques, enabling efficient speed and torque control without mechanical brushes [30], [31]. These drives often use Hall-effect sensors or sensorless techniques to detect rotor position and switch inverter phases accordingly, ensuring smooth and efficient motor operation [32]. Moreover, regulatory policies and incentive schemes from governments across the globe are promoting the adoption of residential solar PV systems. Net metering, feed-in tariffs, and capital subsidies make such systems economically viable and attractive for homeowners [33]. With proper modeling and simulation using tools like MATLAB, the optimal design of a solar-powered home with BLDC motor loads can be achieved, ensuring minimal losses, efficient load sharing, and grid stability [34], [35].

2. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system integrates a solar photovoltaic (PV) array with a grid-connected structure to power both home appliances and a Brushless DC (BLDC) motor as shown in Fig.1. The PV array is modeled in MATLAB/Simulink and configured to convert solar irradiance into DC electricity, which serves as the primary energy source. A DC-DC boost converter is

connected to the PV array to regulate and step up the voltage to a required level. This regulated DC power is then fed into a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) that converts the DC output into AC power suitable for domestic loads. For the BLDC motor, a separate three-phase inverter is employed, which uses electronic commutation techniques to drive the motor based on speed and torque requirements. The system also includes a grid interconnection that ensures power continuity by supplying electricity during periods of low solar generation. Synchronization with the grid is achieved through control logic and phase-lock mechanisms. MATLAB/Simulink is used to simulate the complete system, validating the power flow, voltage regulation, and motor performance under different environmental and load conditions. This setup demonstrates an efficient smart energy system that optimally utilizes solar power for both household use and motor-driven applications.

3. MODELING AND DESIGNING OF PROPOSED CONFIGURATION

Fig.1 Schematic of the grid interactive PV array based for a BLDC motor drive

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{ph} = I_{sc} + k_i(T - 298)H \quad (2)$$

$$I_d = I_o \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + I_{pv}R_s}{AKT}q\right) - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V + I_{pv}R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

where I_{pv} is the terminal current of the PV cell; I_{ph} is the current generated by the incident solar irradiance, I_d is the diode current and I_{sh} is the shunt resistance current; I_{sc} is the short circuit current of the cell, k_i is the array short circuit current temperature coefficient, T is the cell

A. Modeling and designing proposed solar PV system configuration

Photovoltaic (PV) cells generate voltage when sunlight is incident on them. It is the basic building block for converting solar energy into electrical energy. Fig. 2(a) represents the equivalent circuit of PV cells as one diode model [19]. The circuit consists of a current generated by incident solar insolation called photo current (I_{ph}), a diode, a parallel resistance (R_{sh}) and a series resistance (R_s) representing the leakage current and an internal resistance respectively of the PV cell [20]. Each PV cell generates a small voltage of 0.6 V. These cells are connected in series and in parallel to increase the module voltage and module current respectively. Figure 2(b) represents the equivalent circuit of the PV module with N_p cells connected in parallel and N_s cells connected in series. The mathematical equations that describes the I-V characteristics of PV cell are given by (1) to (4).

operating temperature (K), H is the solar radiation in KW/m^2 ; I_o is the diode reverse leakage current, V is the terminal voltage, K is Boltzmann's constant ($1.3806503 \times 10^{-23}$ J/K), q is the electron charge ($1.60217646 \times 10^{-19}$ C); R_{sh} and R_s are the shunt and series resistances of the PV cell in Ω and A is the diode ideality factor and its ideal value is 1. The mathematical equation that describes the I-V characteristics of PV module is given by (5):

Fig. 2. (a) Equivalent circuit model of PV cell, (b) Equivalent circuit of PV module.

B. Solar Boost Converter with P&O MPPT Algorithm

A boost converter is a power electronic circuit used in solar photovoltaic systems to step up the voltage generated by the solar panel as shown in Fig.3. Since the output voltage of a PV module is often lower than what is required for grid connection or to power DC loads, a boost converter increases the voltage to a usable level. It includes an inductor, a power switch such as a MOSFET, a diode, and an output capacitor. When the switch is turned on, the inductor stores energy from the PV panel. When the switch is turned off, the inductor releases this energy to the load through the diode, resulting in a higher output voltage. By adjusting the amount of time the switch remains on and off, referred to as the duty cycle; the output voltage can be controlled. The boost converter ensures that maximum energy from the solar panel is transferred efficiently, making it an essential component in solar power systems.

Fig. 3 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

a. P&O MPPT Algorithm

The P&O MPPT algorithm adjusts the duty cycle (D) of the boost converter based on small perturbations to the PV voltage as shown in Fig.4. The power change is determined as follows:

$$\Delta P = P(k) - P(k - 1) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta V = V(k) - V(k - 1) \quad (6)$$

if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, increase V_{pv}

if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, decrease V_{pv}

if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, decrease V_{pv} (7)

if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, increase V_{pv}

The updated duty cycle is calculated as:

$$D(k + 1) = D(k) + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta P) \quad (8)$$

Where α is the step size for duty cycle adjustment.

Fig.4 flow chart for P&O MPPT algorithm

C. Boost Converter Design

The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC bus voltage. The output voltage of the boost converter is given by:

Fig.5 DC-DC unidirectional boost converter

$$V_o = \frac{V_{pv}}{1 - D} \quad (9)$$

Where: V_o = Output voltage of boost converter (V), V_{pv} = Input PV voltage (V), D = Duty cycle of the converter

The inductor value is selected to ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation:

$$L = \frac{V_{pv}(1-D)}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (10)$$

where: L = Inductor value (H), f_s = Switching frequency (Hz), ΔI_L = Inductor ripple current (A)

The output capacitor is designed to minimize voltage ripples:

$$C = \frac{I_o}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_o} \quad (11)$$

Where: C = Output capacitor (F), I_o = Output current (A), ΔV_o = Allowable voltage ripple (V)

4. MODELING AND DESIGNING OF BLDC MOTOR

The Brushless DC (BLDC) motor is modeled and designed based on the principles of electromagnetic torque generation using electronically commutated stator windings. Unlike conventional DC motors, the BLDC motor does not use brushes for commutation; instead, it employs a three-phase inverter and rotor position sensors, such as Hall-effect sensors, for precise control of the switching sequence. The motor is designed with a permanent magnet rotor and stator windings arranged in a trapezoidal back-EMF configuration to ensure efficient torque production with minimal torque ripple. The mathematical model of the BLDC motor consists of dynamic equations for stator voltage, current, back EMF, and torque generation, implemented in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The inverter used to drive the motor is controlled based on the rotor position feedback, allowing real-time commutation and speed regulation. Parameters such as stator resistance, inductance, and the back EMF constant are carefully selected to match the application requirements. The simulation model incorporates a closed-loop control system that adjusts the motor speed according to the desired set point while maintaining stable operation even under varying load conditions. This modeling approach enables accurate analysis of motor dynamics, efficiency, and performance in the smart energy system.

A. Mathematical Designing of BLDC Motor

The Brushless DC (BLDC) motor is designed using a set of mathematical equations that describe its electrical and mechanical behavior. The BLDC motor consists of a three-phase stator and a permanent magnet rotor. Unlike brushed DC motors, commutation in a BLDC motor is performed electronically through a three-phase inverter,

which is controlled based on the rotor position sensed by Hall-effect sensors.

The stator winding of the BLDC motor follows the basic form of the phase voltage equation, which for each phase can be written as:

$$V_a = R \cdot i_a + L \cdot \frac{di_a}{dt} + e_a \quad (12)$$

$$V_b = R \cdot i_b + L \cdot \frac{di_b}{dt} + e_b \quad (13)$$

$$V_c = R \cdot i_c + L \cdot \frac{di_c}{dt} + e_c \quad (14)$$

Where: V_a, V_b, V_c are the phase voltages, i_a, i_b, i_c are the phase currents, R is the stator resistance per phase, L is the stator inductance per phase, e_a, e_b, e_c are the back electromotive forces (EMF) of each phase

The back-EMF in each phase is dependent on the rotor position and speed, and is expressed as:

$$e_a = f_a(\theta) \cdot \omega \cdot k_e \quad (15)$$

$$e_b = f_b(\theta) \cdot \omega \cdot k_e \quad (16)$$

$$e_c = f_c(\theta) \cdot \omega \cdot k_e \quad (17)$$

Where: $f_a(\theta), f_b(\theta), f_c(\theta)$ are the trapezoidal back-EMF waveforms as a function of rotor position θ , ω is the rotor speed in rad/s, k_e is the back-EMF constant

The electromagnetic torque generated by the motor is given by:

$$T_a = \frac{1}{\omega} (e_a i_a + e_b i_b + e_c i_c) \quad (18)$$

The mechanical equation of the motor governing its rotational dynamics is:

$$T_e - T_L = J \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dt} + B \cdot \omega \quad (19)$$

Where: T_L is the load torque, J is the moment of inertia, B is the damping coefficient

The motor is typically controlled using a six-step (trapezoidal) commutation technique where each pair of inverter switches conducts for 120° electrical duration. Hall-effect sensors or sensorless estimation techniques are used to determine rotor position and enable appropriate switching sequences in the inverter.

IV. BI-DIRECTIONAL POWER FLOW CONTROL

Grid interactive PV generating makes it possible to construct a dependable water pumping system and fully use the resources. As seen in Fig. 6, a bi-directional power regulation based on a UVT generation is used to permit the flow of power in either direction. Since no sophisticated mathematical model or procedure is needed, this is the most straightforward method and is also the easiest to apply. Utility grid voltage and current are synchronized using a single phase PLL (Phase Locked Loop). At the fundamental frequency, it

produces a sinusoidal unit vector of supply voltage, $\sin \theta$. However, by controlling the DC bus voltage, v_{dc} , an amplitude of the fundamental component of supply current, I_{sp} , is extracted. As a voltage regulator, a proportional-integral (PI) controller is used. To suppress the ripple contents, v_{dc} is detected and sent via a first-order low pass filter. Next, a predetermined value, V_{dc}^* , is compared to the filtered VDC. Multiplying I_{sp} by $\sin \theta$ yields i_s^* , a basic component of supply current. The gating pulses for VSC are produced by comparing the measured supply current, i_s , with i_s^* and processing the error via a current controller. The voltage regulator produces a positive I_{sp} when electricity from the utility

is needed. As a result, the grid is used to draw an in-phase supply current. Similarly, an out-of-phase supply current results from a negative I_{sp} created when the utility is supplied by a PV array. Therefore, the direction of power flow may be adjusted as needed by reversing the current. The implemented control technology also guarantees enhanced power quality at the utility grid in terms of power factor and total harmonic distortion (THD). The DC bus voltage cannot be controlled if the grid is unavailable. Despite being weather-sensitive, the PV array may still supply the water pump while operating independently.

FIG.6 Bi-directional power flow control of VSC

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed smart grid-connected solar system integrated with a BLDC motor was simulated using MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate its performance under dynamically changing solar irradiance and motor speed conditions over a 1-second interval as shown in Fig.7. The system includes a 2 kW photovoltaic (PV) array, a boost converter with a Perturb & Observe (P&O) MPPT controller, a three-phase voltage source inverter (VSI), domestic AC loads, and a BLDC motor driven by an electronic commutation scheme. The utility grid is modeled as a stiff voltage source to ensure reliable operation during PV shortfalls. Initially, the system operates under standard test conditions with solar irradiance at 1000 W/m^2 , where the MPPT algorithm effectively tracks the maximum power point, maintaining a stable DC-link voltage around 400 V. At 0.3 seconds, the irradiance drops abruptly to 0 W/m^2 , simulating complete shading. As a result, PV power drops to zero and the grid seamlessly takes over, ensuring uninterrupted supply to the BLDC motor and domestic loads. At 0.7 seconds, irradiance begins to

recover, reaching 500 W/m^2 by 0.8 seconds, allowing partial PV power contribution. However, another drop to 0 W/m^2 occurs at 0.8 seconds, again shifting the full power burden to the grid. Throughout these transitions, the inverter maintains a constant 230 V (rms) AC output with sinusoidal current waveforms and a low Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) of 3.04%, ensuring power quality and system stability. The power factor remains close to unity, demonstrating efficient energy utilization and minimal reactive power exchange. The BLDC motor, connected directly to the DC bus, operates initially at 3000 rad/s. At 0.53 seconds, a command reduces the speed to 1500 rad/s, and the motor responds with a smooth transition and ripple-free torque response. Later, at 0.85 seconds, the speed is adjusted again to 2000 rad/s and is maintained until 1 second, with the motor achieving the transition accurately while sustaining balanced phase currents and stable operation. Voltage and current waveforms confirm that the DC-link remains near 400 V, and the inverter supplies both AC loads and the motor without disruption. The MPPT controller tracks the power curve in real-time, ensuring

minimal energy loss during rapid irradiance fluctuations. During PV shortages, the grid compensates effectively, and during PV availability, surplus energy is exported. These results confirm that the proposed system reliably manages fluctuating solar energy, delivers high-quality power to loads, and maintains BLDC motor performance with minimal losses and fast dynamic response. The simulation validates the system's effectiveness in residential smart energy environments, where real-time power balancing and stable motor operation are essential.

Fig.7 Simulation results for Dynamic response of solar PV with grid for BLDC motor

Fig.8 Grid current THD

6. CONCLUSION

This work successfully demonstrates the design and simulation of a smart grid-connected solar system for residential energy supply and BLDC motor applications using MATLAB/Simulink. The proposed system integrates photovoltaic (PV) panels with an MPPT-controlled boost converter and a voltage source inverter (VSI) to efficiently manage energy flow between the solar source, utility grid, domestic AC loads, and a DC-operated BLDC motor. The implementation of the Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT algorithm ensures maximum power extraction from the PV array under dynamically varying irradiance conditions, while the VSI ensures stable AC output with low Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), maintaining grid compatibility and power quality. The BLDC motor operates with high efficiency and reliability due to the effective electronic

commutation scheme, making it suitable for household applications like water pumping and ventilation. Simulation results validate the system's capability to seamlessly switch between solar and grid supply during low irradiance, while maintaining stable voltage, minimal power losses, and balanced motor operation. The overall system presents a sustainable, scalable, and cost-effective solution for modern smart homes, reducing grid dependency, promoting clean energy usage, and supporting intelligent load management. Future work can extend this model to include battery storage and IoT-based remote monitoring for enhanced energy autonomy and real-time control.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] IEA, "World Energy Outlook 2023", International Energy Agency, 2023.
- [2] REN21, "Renewables 2023 Global Status Report", Renewable Energy Policy Network, 2023.
- [3] A. Luque and S. Hegedus, *Handbook of Photovoltaic Science and Engineering*, Wiley, 2011.
- [4] B. Parida, S. Iniyar, R. Goic, "A review of solar photovoltaic technologies," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2011.
- [5] G. Masson et al., "Global Market Outlook for Solar Power 2022-2026", SolarPower Europe.
- [6] B. Kroposki et al., "Achieving a 100% Renewable Grid," *IEEE Power & Energy Magazine*, 2017.
- [7] S. Mekhilef, R. Saidur, A. Safari, "A review on solar energy use in industries," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2011.
- [8] MathWorks, "MATLAB Simulink Documentation," The MathWorks Inc., 2024.
- [9] S. Jain and V. Agarwal, "Comparative study of maximum power point tracking techniques for solar PV systems using MATLAB," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 2007.
- [10] H. Patel and V. Agarwal, "Maximum power point tracking scheme for PV systems using single-stage inverter topology," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, 2008.
- [11] N. Femia et al., "Optimization of perturb and observe MPPT algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 2005.
- [12] T. ESRAM and P. Chapman, "Comparison of photovoltaic array maximum power point tracking techniques," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, 2007.
- [13] M. A. Elgendy et al., "An improved incremental conductance MPPT algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 2013.
- [14] N. Pandiarajan, Ranganath Muthu, "Mathematical modeling of PV module with Simulink," *International Conference on Electrical Energy Systems*, 2011.
- [15] N. Mohan, *Power Electronics: Converters, Applications and Design*, Wiley, 2003.
- [16] J. F. Gieras, M. Wing, *Permanent Magnet Motor Technology*, CRC Press, 2002.
- [17] C. Xia, *Permanent Magnet Brushless DC Motor Drives and Controls*, Wiley, 2012.
- [18] Y. Chen and K. T. Chau, "An overview of energy management in hybrid electric vehicles," *Energy Conversion and Management*, 2006.
- [19] S. S. Williamson, A. K. Rathore, "Brushless DC motor drive with power factor corrected front-end converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 2010.
- [20] B. Singh et al., "Grid interfacing of renewable energy sources with power quality improvement," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 2011.
- [21] Y. Yang, F. Blaabjerg, "Power control strategies for grid-connected PV inverters with enhanced functionality," *Energies*, 2015.
- [22] M. Islam, S. Mekhilef, "Power quality enhancement of grid-connected PV system," *Energy Conversion and Management*, 2014.
- [23] A. Q. Huang, M. L. Crow, et al., "The future renewable electric energy delivery and management (FREEDM) system," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 2011.
- [24] S. A. Kalpande, P. P. Bedekar, "MPPT based solar water pumping system using BLDC motor," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 2016.
- [25] K. Karki et al., "Performance evaluation of grid-connected PV system in MATLAB/Simulink," *IEEE International Conference on Power Electronics*, 2019.
- [26] B. Subudhi, R. Pradhan, "A comparative study on maximum power point tracking techniques for PV power systems," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 2013.
- [27] R. Bell and R. Lasseter, "Digital control of voltage source inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 1997.
- [28] H. Mahmood, D. Michaelson, J. Jiang, "Control strategy for a stand-alone PV/battery hybrid system," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, 2015.
- [29] G. Walker, "Evaluating MPPT converter topologies using a MATLAB PV model," *Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, 2001.
- [30] R. Krishnan, *Electric Motor Drives: Modeling, Analysis, and Control*, Prentice Hall, 2001.
- [31] T. Kenjo, S. Nagamori, *Permanent-Magnet and Brushless DC Motors*, Clarendon Press, 1985.
- [32] Y. S. Lee, "Sensorless control of BLDC motors using back EMF," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 2008.
- [33] MNRE India, "Grid Connected Solar Rooftop Systems and Net Metering," Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, 2022.
- [34] IEEE, "Standard for Interconnection and Interoperability of Distributed Energy Resources with Associated Electric Power Systems Interfaces," IEEE Std 1547-2018.
- [35] S. Arulmurugan, "Simulation and implementation of grid connected PV system with BLDC motor load," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, 2019.